

**SYNTHESIS OF CYANINE DYES BY THE CONDENSATION OF
p-DIETHYLAMINOBENZALDEHYDE WITH APPROPRIATE
HETEROCYCLIC COMPOUNDS. PART IX**

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Three new dyes have been prepared by the condensation of *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde with 6-formamido-, 6-acetamido- and 5-acetamido-quinolidine ethiodide, and one more by condensing *p*-diethylaminobenzaldehyde with 5-acetamidoquinaldine ethiodide. The absorption maxima and sensitisation spectra of these four substituted dyes have been recorded. The chemical and other properties have been studied.

Among the various heterocyclic compounds used in the synthesis of the very large number of cyanine dyes, now known, quinoline derivatives are by far the most generally used.

The present work deals with the preparation and the study of the properties of four new styrylcyanines. Three of these were prepared by the condensation of *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde with 6-formamido-, 6-acetamido- and 5-acetamido-quinolidine ethiodide, and another by the condensation of *p*-diethylaminobenzaldehyde with 5-acetamidoquinaldine ethiodide, in absolute ethanol in presence of piperidine as catalyst. The object of the present investigation was to study the effect of the substituents introduced in the 6-position and in the 5-position of *p*-dialkylaminostyrylquinoline ethiodide. The dyes may be represented by the general expression (I : R = Me or Et) :

which represents the resonance hybrid between the two extreme canonical forms, the anion being attached to the heterocyclic N atom in one, and to the exocyclic N atom in the other.

It will be apparent from the structure of the dyes, now prepared, that variations have been effected by weighting the parent dye molecule by (i) suitable substitution in the heterocyclic nucleus, and (ii) condensing the heterocyclic nuclei, thus obtained, with *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde in place of the *p*-diethyl analogue, the intervening polymethine chain being the same. Some of the results of these investigations have already been reported (Doja and Sinha, this *Journal*, 1954, 31, 735 ; 1956, 33, 183).

The heterocyclic bases, required for the present investigation, were quaternised by heating them with ethyl iodide in sealed tubes on the water-bath for varying periods.

Methanol was uniformly used as a solvent for crystallisation. The dyes are obtained as well-formed pleochroic crystals, possessing various degrees of reflex. The rectified spirit solutions of these dyes are all coloured violet with a pronounced reddish tinge.

By the addition of mineral acids, the colour of the solutions is completely discharged and is probably due to the destruction of the conjugated system which is responsible for the colour (cf. Brooker *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 62, 1116).

A measure of the relative resistance to decolorisation has been obtained by titrating 2 c.c. of 1 : 50,000 solution of the dye in ethanol with *N*/100-HCl, figures for which are shown in Table I. The dimethylamino dye (G_1) has been found to be more resistant to decolorisation than the corresponding diethylamino compound.

TABLE I

Symbol of dye.	Colour and shape of the crystals	Reflex.	Pleochroism.		<i>N</i> /100 HCl reqd.	Relative resistance to decolorisation.
			Colour of light in one position of polariser	Colour after rotation through 90°.		
F_1	Dark mauve powder	Weak green	Opaque	Grey	16.0 c.c.	2.58
F_1	Deep magenta powder	Nil	Dark grey	Opaque	19.0	3.06
G_1	Felt green crystals	Shining green	Opaque	Translucent	41.2	6.64
G	Dirty red leaves	Nil	Dark red	Opaque	6.2	1.00
E_1	2- <i>p</i> -Dimethylaminostyryl-6-formamidquinoline ethide.					
F_1	2- <i>p</i> - " " " -6-acetamido " "					
G_1	2- <i>p</i> - " " " -5-acetamido " "					
G	2- <i>p</i> -Diethyl " " -5-acetamido " "					

All these dyes are readily soluble in methanol, ethanol and glacial acetic acid. These dyes also show the peculiar phenomenon that their acetic acid solutions deepen in colour on warming and their original colours are regained on cooling, the effect being more pronounced in aqueous acetic acid solutions (cf. Doja and Sinha, *loc. cit.*).

The various shades, produced on silk, cotton and wool from ethanolic solutions of these dyes are shown in Table II. The shades are fugitive to exposure and washing.

TABLE II

Compound ...	F_1	F_1	G_1	G
Silk ...	Rose-red	Reddish violet	Reddish violet	Indigo-violet
Wool ...	Maroon	Reddish violet	Maroon	Violet
Cotton ...	Rose-pink	Pink-violet	Reddish blue	Brijal-blue

The fluorescence of weak alcoholic solutions (1 : 100,000) of the dyes (cf. Doja, *this Journal*, 1940, 17, 347) are recorded in Table III.

TABLE III

Wallace colour filter No.	Colour of the fluorescent beam seen at right angle to the incident beam passing through solution of the dyes.			
	E_1 .	F_1 .	G_1 .	G.
1.	Light absorbed	Crimson	Flaming red	Light absorbed
2.	Orange-yellow	Orange-red	Reddish yellow	Reddish yellow
3.	Yellowish red	Yellowish red	Violet	Pink
4.	Flaming red	Flaming red	Orange-yellow	Reddish yellow
5.	Flaming red	Orange-yellow	Reddish yellow	Orange-yellow
6.	Reddish yellow	Reddish yellow	Flaming yellow	Reddish yellow
7.	Lemon-yellow	Yellow	Light violet	Lemon-yellow
8.	Light violet	Violet	Deep violet	Deep pink
9.	Orange-red	Orange-yellow	Orange-red	Reddish yellow
10.	Violet	Light absorbed	Light absorbed	Violet

The sensitisation spectra are shown in Fig. 1. For the sake of comparison, the sensitisation spectrum of an unbathed process plate is appended (Fig. 1). The absorption maxima of all these dyes have been determined in absolute ethanol on a Beckman DU model spectrophotometer.

FIG. 1

The absorption maxima, logarithmic values of molar extinction coefficient and ranges of extra-sensitisations are recorded in Table IV.

TABLE IV

Dye	Nature of substitution.	λ_{max} .	log ϵ .	Extra-sensitisation.		Remarks.
				Range.	Max.	
E ₁	6-HCONH	529 m μ	3.95	3580-7040 Å	5400 Å	Fairly uniform
F ₁	6-MeCONH	537	4.68	3540-6950	4460	from 4400 to
G ₁	5-MeCONH	540	4.82	3500-6640	4480	6200 Å with minor
G	5-MeCONH	552	4.81	3480-6580	4500	peak at 5400 Å.

It will be observed that the 5-acetamido-*p*-diethylaminostyryl compound absorbs at a longer wave-length than its dimethyl analogue. This is in conformity with the general observation that the weighting of the dye molecule by heavier groups shifts the absorption maxima towards longer wave-lengths. Substitution at 6-position by groups of increasing molecular weights, e.g., formamido by acetamido group, shifted the absorption maxima to longer wave-length. Thus, the substituents have the following sequence: 5-acetamido-(*p*-diethyl) > 5-acetamido-(*p*-dimethyl) > 6-acetamido-(*p*-dimethyl) > 6-formamido-(*p*-dimethyl).

It is interesting to note here that the 6-substituted acetamido dyes have longer range of extra-sensitisation than the 5-substituted acetamido dyes in either of the *p*-diethylamino and the *p*-dimethylamino series. The extra-sensitisation conferred by the dyes are of the order: 6-formamido-(*p*-dimethyl) > 6-acetamido-(*p*-dimethyl) > 5-acetamido-(*p*-diethyl).

Curiously enough, the 5-acetamido-*p*-dimethyl dye is a better sensitiser than the corresponding *p*-diethyl dye, while the latter absorbs at a large wave-length than the former. Though these dyes absorb at longer wave-lengths than their 6-acetamido analogues, they are, however, comparatively weak sensitisers.

EXPERIMENTAL

2-p-Dimethylaminostyryl-6-formamidoquinoline Ethiodide.—*p*-Dimethylaminobenzaldehyde (0.14 g.), 6-formamidoquinaldine ethiodide (0.3 g.), absolute ethanol (10 c.c.) and piperidine (2 drops) were boiled under reflux for 2 hours, when a deep red colour of the solution was developed. The dye (0.15 g.) separating on cooling was recrystallised from methanol, m.p. 240° (shrinking from 233°). (Found: N, 8.55; I, 26.9. C₂₂H₂₁ON₂I requires N, 8.87; I, 26.85%).

2-p-Dimethylaminostyryl-6-acetamidoquinoline Ethiodide.—On refluxing under a moisture trap an ethanolic solution (30 c.c.) of 6-acetamidoquinaldine ethiodide (0.71 g.), *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde (0.298 g.) and piperidine (4 drops), an intense magenta colour developed. The heating was continued for 1 hour. The dye separating during later period of heating was recrystallised from methanol, m.p. 283°, yield 0.4 g. (Found: N, 8.65; I, 26.2. C₂₃H₂₃ON₂I requires N, 8.63; I, 26.07%).

5-Acetamidoquinaldine Ethiodide.—5-Acetamidoquinaldine (1.1 g.) and ethyl iodide (1.5 g.) were heated at 100° in a sealed tube for 27 hours. The solid mass was washed with ether to remove any unchanged base, extracted with hot water and filtered. The

filtrate on evaporation afforded an oily product, which was then dissolved in alcohol and precipitated with ether as a yellowish green solid, yield 0.75 g., m.p. 203-204°, shrinking from 197°. (Found: I, 35.8. $C_{14}H_{17}ON_2I$ requires I, 35.67%).

2-p-Dimethylaminostyryl-5-acetamidoquinoline Ethiodide.—A solution of *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde (0.335 g.), 5-acetamidoquinoline ethiodide (0.8 g.) in absolute ethanol (30 c.c.) were refluxed in a small conical flask for 2 hours with 3 drops of piperidine, under a moisture trap. The dye (0.35 g.) crystallised out on cooling and was recrystallised from methanol as clusters of small needles, m.p. 258.5°. (Found: N, 8.7; I, 25.8. $C_{23}H_{26}ON_3I$ requires N, 8.62; I, 26.07%).

2-p-Diethylaminostyryl-5-acetamidoquinoline Ethiodide.—By refluxing a hot solution of 5-acetamidoquinoline ethiodide (0.712 g.) and *p*-diethylaminobenzaldehyde (0.354 g.) in absolute ethanol (30 c.c.) with piperidine (4 drops) under a calcium chloride guard tube for 35 minutes, the dye began to separate. A further amount deposited on cooling. The collected samples (0.6 g.) were recrystallised from methanol as copper-red woolly clusters, m.p. 264-65°. (Found: N, 8.0; I, 24.8. $C_{23}H_{26}ON_3I$ requires N, 8.1; I, 24.66%).

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Received December 17, 1953.